

A NOTE ON THE PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF SODIUM HYPONITRITE

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Sodium hyponitrite pentahydrate has been prepared by the method of Divers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 47, 97) modified by Partington and Shah (*ibid.*, 1931, 2071). 2.8622 G. of hydrated substance left 1.5484 g. of anhydrous substance giving off 1.3138 g. of H_2O i.e., $5H_2O$. The analytical results of this substance have been given (Oza, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 70).

If nitrogen was not bubbled during the treatment with the amalgam the crystals first obtained from the strong caustic lye consisted of pure Na_2CO_3 and the subsequent lots contained Na_2CO_3 mixed with increasing amounts of $Na_2N_2O_3$ till the fifth crop of crystals, obtained on intensive desiccation, contained pure $Na_2N_2O_3$. The substance, thus formed, was the trihydrate. Another experiment showed that even when nitrogen was bubbled and pure pentahydrate obtained in the normal manner if the mother liquors, containing the hyponitrite, were allowed to stand for a long time (three months) in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid, the crystals formed consisted of pure trihydrate :

- (i) 2.3005 G. crystals left 1.5229 g. anhydrous substance so that for 106 g. $Na_2N_2O_3$, this is 54.16 g. H_2O i.e., $3H_2O$.
- (ii) 0.8007 G. crystals left 0.5232 g. anhydrous substance so that for 106 g. $Na_2N_2O_3$, this is 56.2 g. H_2O i.e., $3H_2O$.

The anhydrous substance corresponding to (i) and (ii) above did not contain any nitrite or carbonate and when analysed by the volumetric method (Oza and Walawalker, unpublished work) was found to consist of pure $Na_2N_2O_3$.

Properties of $Na_2N_2O_3$.—The substance crystallises in beautiful greyish prisms reflecting light at many points. When dehydrated, the crystals crumble to dull white powder. Even a very minute (microscopic) amount of the substance gives a beautiful heavy canary yellow characteristic precipitate with $AgNO_3$. When treated with KI in acidic medium, iodine is not liberated instantaneously as with nitrite but only on standing for a few seconds. This is peculiar since nitrites liberate iodine instantaneously even when present in very very minute amounts.

Resorcinol and periodate have been reported to yield characteristic colour with hyponitrites (Corbet, *Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 1375 ; 1940, 34, 1029). This has been refuted by Rao (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 599) and by Rao and Sastry (*ibid.*, 1942, 19, 188). A sharp colour change was not observed in this case as well in the mixture of saturated potassium paraperiodate solution and $M/5$ -resorcinol (10 c.c. each) on the addition of sodium hyponitrite. The only change noticeable was the transition from the reddish brown colour of the mixture to a more distinctly brownish tinge (p_H of mixture was greater than 9). The test was carefully carried out as there has been a prolonged controversy on its reliability. With pure sodium hyponitrite and potassium paraperiodate, prepared according to Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1088) having molecular weight of 303.35 (303.2 and 303.5), the colour was noticed over the whole p_H range from strongly

alkaline solution obtained on admixture, to neutral and distinctly acidic range obtained on slow addition of an acid to the mixture. The p_{H} of the neutral and acidic ranges was determined potentiometrically using quinhydrone-calomel chain. The highest acidity used had p_{H} of 2.4. The only thing noticed was the development of more and more reddish tinge with increase in acidity of the solution. The original solution of the reagents was reddish, became brownish with alkalinity and again reddish with loss of alkalinity. It was ascertained that in the acid of the concentrations used, the sodium hyponitrite did not all decompose.

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